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Department of Sanskrit
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E-mail : vaichariki@gmail.com

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Personal Space amongst Women in Context of Emotional Intelligence and Marital Adjustment

*Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Kumar**

The study was conducted on 100 married male respondents to examine the effect of emotional intelligence and marital adjustment on personal space of the respondents. It was hypothesized that (i) there would be significant influence of emotional intelligence on personal space of the respondents. (ii) there would be significant influence of marital adjustment on personal space of the respondents. (iii) there would be significant relationship between emotional intelligence and marital adjustment of the respondents. For the purpose, Mangal's Emotional Intelligence Scale, MAQ by Kumar and Rohtagi along with a PDS were administered on the respondents to measure emotional intelligence, marital adjustment and to get necessary information about the respondents. Personal space was measured experimentally. The respondents belonging to high emotional intelligence group and sound marital adjustment group maintained smaller personal space than their counterparts. It was concluded that personal space is a function of emotional intelligence and marital adjustment. Further, emotional intelligence and marital adjustment was found significantly and positively correlated.

Introduction

Present study embodies concepts like personal space, emotional intelligence and marital adjustment need explanation. Personal space is concerned with the subjective manner of stimulating and maintaining comfortable physical distance to relevant other people in personal and social life. Personal space can be defined as the area, individual human actively maintain around themselves, into which others cannot intrude without arousing discomfort (Reber et al. 2009).

Emotional intelligence, the next component, refers to the abilities to perceive emotions, to access and general emotions so as to assist thought to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to effectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotions and intellectual growth (Mayer and Solovey, 1997).

The next component is marital adjustment which refers to adjustment relating to marriage affairs. Marriage provides a person an opportunity for a secure and protected satisfaction of his needs for companionship affection and sexual expression. It involves the most intimate type of emotional relationship between two individual (Coleman, 1964). Many marriages suffer because the two partners fail to develop a relationship which is characterized by mutual acceptance, trust, care, concern, love, admiration and sharing of role responsibilities.

Various personal factors like age, sex, education, familiarity etc. have deep impact on the preference of personal space. Besides, there are personality factors, cultural factors and situational factors affecting personal space. Folarin (1980) found that space preference varies with grade and sex of interacting pairs of children. McDowell (1972) tried to study behavioural manifestation at the violation of personal space. Several studies showing the effect of personal variables on personal space have been made. But there are negligible Indian

* University Professor, Dept. of Psychology, College of Commerce, Arts and Science, Patna, Patliputra University, Patna

studies relating to the impact of emotional intelligence and marital adjustment on personal space and hence the undertaking of this study is justified.

Objectives : The following were the objectives of the study : (i) to examine the influence of emotional intelligence on personal space of the respondents, (ii) to examine the influence of marital adjustment on personal space of the respondents and (iii) to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and marital adjustment.

Hypotheses : (i) There would be significant influence of emotional intelligence on personal space of the respondents, (ii) There would be significant influence of marital adjustment on personal space of the respondents, and (iii) There would be significant relationship between emotional intelligence and marital adjustment.

Method of Study

Sample Used : An incidental-cum-purposive sample consisting of 100 married males were selected from different organization. They were selected individually as well as in small groups as per their convenience. In other respect, they were matched so far as practicable.

Tools Used : The following tools were used : (i) A Personal Data Sheet was employed to get the necessary information about the respondents, (ii) Mangal's Emotional Intelligence Scale was employed on the respondents to measure emotional intelligence of the respondents (iii) Marital Adjustment Questionnaire by Kumar and Rahtogi was used to measure marital adjustment of the respondents. (iv) Personal Space of the respondents was measured individually using experimental method.

Procedure of Data Collection : The Scale along with PDS were employed on the respondents and their data were determined. The median value on emotional intelligence score and MAQ score were determined. Thereafter, the respondents at and above the median value were placed into high groups and the respondents falling below the median value were placed into low groups. In this way using median as cut the respondents were grouped into high and low emotional intelligence as well as marital adjustment groups respectively. Thereafter, for measuring personal space the subjects were called individually and were asked to take a comfortable seat before the researcher. The distance from the researcher maintained by the subject was measured. In the same manner the personal space of all the respondents was measured.

Results and Interpretation

Table-01

t-ratio showing the influence of emotional intelligence on personal space of the respondents.

Emotional Intelligence	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	p
Low	62	22.59	6.24	6.62	98	<.01
High	38	15.44	4.53			

The result contained in table-1 clearly revealed the significant influence of emotional intelligence on personal space of the respondents ($t = 6.62$; $df = 98$; $P < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. (1) is retained. The finding might be interpreted in terms of the fact the smaller personal space preferred by the respondents of high emotional intelligence group of respondents might be attributed to the characteristics & emotional intelligence. They do not want to behave like commoners. Their high level of confidence compels them to maintain respectable smaller distance with other people resulting in to smaller personal space the their counterparts.

Table-02

t-ratio showing the influence of marital adjustment on personal space of the respondents.

Marital Adjustment	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	p
Poor	66	23.11	6.38	7.10	98	<.01
Sound	34	15.37	4.38			

The results displayed in table-2 shows the superiority of respondents belonging to sound marital adjustment group of respondents in terms of maintaining smaller personal space than their counterparts ($t = 7.10$; $df = 98$; $P < .01$). The second hypothesis is confirmed. The finding might be interpreted on the ground of that the respondents of sound marital adjustment group are self-confident, self-reliant, emotionally balanced and tended to internalise people easily and confidently leading to maintenance of smaller personal space than their counterpart respondents with poor marital adjustment group.

Table-03

r-showing significance of relationship between emotional intelligence score and marital adjustment score.

Variables	N	r	df	p
Emotional Intelligence Score Vs Marital Adjustment Score	100	0.517	98	<.01

The results of table-03 clearly revealed a significant positive correlation between emotional intelligence and marital adjustment ($r = 0.517$; $df = 98$; $P < .01$). The finding is constant with the findings of table-01 and table-02 respectively.

Conclusions

- (i) High emotional intelligence is conducive to maintenance of smaller personal space.
- (ii) Sound marital adjustment is conducive to maintenance of smaller personal space.
- (iii) Emotional intelligence and marital adjustment are positively and significantly correlated.

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